

INITIATIVES OF UZBEKISTAN REGARDING PEACE AND COOPERATION IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract The article analyzes the role of Uzbekistan in ensuring regional security and cooperation between Central Asian countries. Also, conclusions and suggestions were given on the importance of the role of Uzbekistan in ensuring regional security and cooperation in Central Asia.

Key words: democracy, peace, interests, strategy, values, external factor, neighborhood

The political processes that determine the stable development of the state and society are directly related to the internal and external factors of this country. Until these factors gain socio-political importance and develop, the human phenomenon, its destiny, national interests, national and religious tolerance, inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity will remain in the whirlpool of one-sided or superficial views. In this sense, in the society of Uzbekistan, the development of regional issues, the development of mutual neighborly relations, recognition of the unity of values and interests towards a common goal, in the last five years, effective and comprehensive cooperation relations with the countries of Central Asia have been given a broad tone.

Uzbekistan is located at the intersection of civilizations, different cultural layers, different beliefs and worldviews. The Uzbek people, who make up the majority of the population, have played an important role in regional unity since ancient times. "Uzbekistan today is not only rich natural raw material reserves, unlimited market and investment area. At the moment, our country has enormous intellectual, spiritual and cultural potential. All this, in a situation where a new political and economic order is

actively forming in the world, combined with the unique geographical location of our country, arouses great geo-political and geo-strategic interest"

Uzbekistan, which is a pillar of peace and stability in Central Asia, geographical location in the region, economic potential, military capability, population, international reputation, and ancient traditions of statehood make it possible to fulfill these tasks. As noted by the experienced diplomat and scientist S. Safoev, "a set of factors such as geographical location, economic potential, and population determine not only the position of Uzbekistan in the region, but also its special responsibility for this situation".

The agrarian sector occupies a significant place in the economy of the countries of the region. The ancient farming experience of the agrarian sector has been preserved here. Irrigated agriculture was formed in our country in the IV millennium BC. The evidentiary objects found in the Zamonbobo settlement and similar cultural monuments confirm our opinion. Based on these experiences, our country occupies a leading position in the world in cotton growing, horticulture, and vegetable growing.

In the 21st century, communication has become a factor that ensures development. It is of incomparable importance for Central Asia, which has great natural resources. Taking this into account, the countries of the region are trying to establish new routes that take their resources to the world market. The solution of this problem is of great importance for the economic development of the countries. It prevents them from depending on external forces. On the initiative of the Government of Uzbekistan, work is being carried out in the following directions in this matter. These are:

a) Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran route. The railway connects the Central Asian countries with the Iranian port of Bandar-Abbas. This project, in which Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan participate, will reduce access to sea ports in Central Asia by 4,500 km compared to the current route.

b) The Uzbekistan-Kazakhstan-China route connects Central Asia with the Chinese ports of Lianyungan and Shanghai.

v) The Trans-Afghan route connects the region with Uzbekistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-Indian Ocean and increases cargo transportation efficiency by 1.5-2 times. The region has huge oil and gas reserves. At the time when the demand for these resources is increasing in the world market, pipelines are of great importance. In this regard, the gas pipeline system of Uzbekistan occupies a special place. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan supply gas to our country, and Turkmenistan, which has the largest gas reserves in the region, uses Uzbekistan's gas pipeline system to export its gas.

g) Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman transport corridor. This transport corridor, initiated by Uzbekistan, connects the region with the Persian and Oman Gulfs. On April 25, 2011, an intergovernmental agreement on the creation of the Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman-Qatar transport corridor was signed in Ashgabat. On August 7, 2014, a Memorandum on the implementation of the project between Uzbekistan - Turkmenistan - Iran - Oman was signed in Mashhad, the capital of Oman. The accession of Kazakhstan to this agreement in 2015 showed that the transport corridor is of great importance for our region. In the future, Russia and China may join this project.

d) Uzbekistan-Kyrgyzstan-China railway. This project will also connect the region with China by rail. In the future, as a result of the addition of Turkmenistan to this project, there will be an opportunity to connect China with the Persian Gulf.

It is known that regional problems are one of the main obstacles to development. The government of Uzbekistan has a positive influence on regional cooperation with its pragmatic views on the origin of regional problems, its prevention, and practical activities in their elimination. Since the first years of independence, our country has been taking a serious approach to solving the problems in the region and trying to attract the attention of the world community. These include the elimination of the civil war in Afghanistan and Tajikistan (1992-1997), regional security, religious extremism and terrorism. The initiative of the Uzbek leadership to establish the "6+3" dialogue

group aimed at eliminating instability in Afghanistan, or its efforts to prevent the emergence of inter-ethnic conflicts as a result of the Osh events in Kyrgyzstan in the summer of 2010, were supported by the international community.

Uzbekistan played a leading military-strategic role in preventing the conflicts between Tajikistan and Afghanistan from spreading to the entire region. The role of our country in solving the problems that have arisen in the region is recognized by the world's leading scientists. Many researchers have shown this in their works. Z. Brzezinskiy expresses his opinion that the independence of Uzbekistan will play an important role in the survival of other countries in Central Asia, and it can be the main force against Russia's policy to establish dominance in the region.

The first president of our republic put forward the idea of warning against the threat posed by evil forces, which are rapidly entering the region, and the need for cooperation in the fight against it, from the early days of the emergence of independent states in the region. He drew the attention of the world community to the difficult situation in Afghanistan in the early 1990s and made clear proposals to solve it.

The service of Uzbekistan in ensuring security in the region is that it did not allow the problem of Afghanistan and Tajikistan to spread to the region and was active in eliminating them.

Thus, "Uzbekistan's role" in the development of Central Asia is important in the region due to its economic potential, wealth of raw materials, labor force and demographic potential, military power, and geopolitical location. Any threat to Uzbekistan affects the entire region.

Uzbekistan's initiatives in the process of cooperation and its results are also an important issue.

As regional cooperation is considered a guarantee of stability and development of Central Asia, Uzbekistan is interested in the development of these processes. In the words of S. Safoev, "...the successful development of multifaceted regional cooperation first of all is in the interests of Uzbekistan." At the same time, according

to its position and position, Uzbekistan can influence the course of cooperation processes in Central Asia more than anyone else.

In the early years of independence, the leadership of Uzbekistan realized the need to develop cooperation processes in the region and put forward the idea of "Our common home of Turkestan" as its ideological basis. As noted by the first President of Uzbekistan I. Karimov, this slogan is aimed at continuing the historical traditions existing in the region, enriching them in new historical conditions, and thereby establishing strong brotherly relations between our peoples".

The native population of Uzbekistan is made up of Uzbeks. Also, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples live in our country, such as Karakalpaks, Tajiks, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Tatars, Crimean Tatars, Azerbaijanis, Bashkirs, Slavs. All conditions have been created so that their national rights and customs are not discriminated against. Teaching in seven languages is introduced in schools, the principle of social justice is followed in matters of selection and placement of personnel, distribution of culture and spiritual wealth. Newspapers, books, textbooks, training manuals and other literature are published in seven languages. Television broadcasts and radio broadcasts have been launched to meet the needs of many nations. Representatives of other nationalities are widely involved in state and public affairs.

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